

A NEW AND VERIFIED CASE SUGGESTIVE OF REINCARNATION BASED ON DREAMS AND FLASHBACKS

BY DIETER HASSLER

Dream-based cases	p. 1
Confirmations and private notes	p. 3
Additional information to the article	p. 8
Questions and additional information after publication	p. 9

Dream-based cases

I divide dream-based cases into three categories:

1. “solved” / “unsolved” cases (“solved” indicating that a previous person appearing in the dream was located either through documentation or by witness statements).
2. “anecdotal” / “confirmed through witnesses” (“anecdotal” indicating unverified reports)
3. “dreams only” / “dreams and more” (“dreams and more” means that the information about a previous life is not solely based on dreams but also on other experiences)

The table compiles the literature into these three categories:

	unsolved		solved	
	anecdotal	witnessed	anecdotal	witnessed
Dreams only	See label „1“ below the table	Stevenson 2003, p. 176		Grubbs 2006
Dreams and more	Banerjee 1980, p. 169; Bowman 2003, p. 13; Bowman 2016; Fenwick 1999, p. 101; Gershom 1997, p. 263; Holzer 1994, p. 185, 260; Hardo 2012, p. 75; Kent 2003; Mills 1994, p. 313, 315; Muller 1970, p. 96, 127; Rogo 1985, p. 28-32; Schlotterbeck 1987, p. 24; Stearn 1994, p. 136; Steiger 1996a, p. 1; Stevenson 2003, p. 187	Jacobson 1973, p. 75; Stevenson 2003, p. 197; 205	Allgeier 1984, p. 141; Banerjee 1980, p. 40; Hassler 2015, p. 338, 373; Karlen 1997	Carpenter 1995, p. 88; Hassler 2011, p. 142; 172, list: 214; Hassler 2015, p. 218; Lasch 2004, p. 61; Wieczorek 2015

1: (Allgeier 1988, p. 301; Banerjee 1980, p. 171, 172; Cranston 1984, p. 82; Fenwick 1999, p. 99, 100, 103, 104; Gershom 1997, p. 346, 357; Hardo 2012, p. 80, 86; Holzer 1970, p. 247; Holzer 1994, p. 185f, 336; Holzer 1994a, p. 179ff; Krippner 2002, p. 130, 131, 132; Lenz 1979, p. 34f; Lucas 1993, p. 251; Lucas 1993a, p. 211, 250; McDonald 1985, p. 219ff; Mills 1994, p. 311; Muller 1970, p. 93, 95; Schmidt 1962, p. 124, 157, 256; Steiger 1973, p. 28, 34; Steiger 1996, p. 141, 178; Stemman 1995, p. 16; Stevenson 2003, p. 165, 168, 173; Ward 2008, p. 26)

In some cases the information about a previous life is not solely based on dreams but also on spontaneous memories¹, flashbacks², past-life regressions³, recognitions⁴, mediumistic communications⁵ or near-death experiences⁶.

Stevenson describes 12 successfully verified Asian cases, in which besides children's spontaneous memories also dreams or nightmares appeared, the contents of which coincided with the conscious memories of a previous life⁷. Titus Rivas points out that dreams also play a significant role in some of Stevenson's unsolved cases (Rivas, 2016).

REFERENCES TO DREAM-BASED CASES

p. 10

¹ Bowman 2003, p. 13; Hassler 2011, p. 142, 172, Liste 214; Hassler 2015, p. 218, 338; Mills 1994, p. 315; Karlen 1997

² Holzer 1994, p. 260; Karlen 1997; Steiger 1996a, p. 1; Wieczorek 2015. Anecdotal reports about flashbacks possibly from a former life without the involvement of dreams are found in Carpenter 1995, p. 174; Berger 1991, p. 19f, Fenwick 1999, p. 106f; Holzer 1970, p. 250; Lenz 1979, p. 26, 27, 30, 39, 41, 57; Rogo 1985, p. 32-34;

³ Bowman 2016; Gershom 1997, p. 263 = Hardo 2012, p. 75; Hassler 2015, p. 338, 373; Holzer 1994, p. 260; Kent 2003; Lasch 2004, p. 61; Schlotterbeck 1987, p. 24; Stearn 1994, p. 136

⁴ Allgeier 1984, p. 141; Banerjee 1980, p. 169; Carpenter 1995, p. 88; Fenwick 1999, p. 101; Holzer 1994, p. 185, 260; Jacobson 1973, p. 75; Mills 1994, p. 313; Rogo 1985, p. 28-32; Stevenson 2003, p. 187, 197, 205

⁵ Banerjee 1980, p. 40; Muller 1970, p. 96

⁶ Muller 1970, p. 127

⁷ List in Stevenson 1997, p. 737, 888, 1386 or Hassler 2011, p. 214; typical examples: Hassler 2011, p. 172; Hassler 2015, p. 218

Confirmations and private notes

E-Mail from Rudolf Holzer dated 28.2.2016 to me:

My experience with Udo Wieczorek and Manfred Bomm:

During a phone conversation Udo asked me to look for a fallen soldier named Vinz who died in August 1915 at the Seikofel. He did not know the surname. I found a fallen soldier by the name Vinzenz and I contacted Udo.

We met in Sexten – the first meeting – and Udo told me about his dreams. He showed me the two pieces of paper that I also read and had a transcript made.

On the list of fallen soldiers there was a note of Vinzenz' home town but we could not determine whether this person and the Vinz seen by Udo in his dreams were identical. That is why I put Udo and Manfred in touch with a Franciscan monk in Bozen who had put together the list of fallen soldiers. Everything further they should investigate with the monk.

We met a few more times in Sexten.

Signature of Rudolf Holzer on a confirmation I had sent him and stating that all passages of the book concerning his collaboration are true.

E-Mail from Siegfried Volgger dated 9.12.2015 to me:

Dear Mr Hassler,

With this Email I confirm that I have been interviewed regarding this case by Manfred Bomm and Udo Wieczorek and that I contributed to their research. My contribution in the book "Seelenvermächtnis" is the whole truth and nothing but the truth and is of course a true depiction.

In addition I admire the two authors that worked on this endeavour so diligently and with great responsibility.

With kind regards

Fr. Siegfried Volgger ofm

First Email from Mariangela dated 3.12.2015 to me:

Dear Mr Hassler,

I am Mariangela Giolito, the daughter-in-law of Ms Giuseppina Rossi Weiss. She does not know any German.

My husband and I met and got to know Udo and Manfred on 25. August 2013. Everything happened just as it is described in the book.

With kind regards

Mariangela Giolito Weiss

Second Email from Mariangel dated 03.12.2015 to me:

Dear Mr Hassler,

I am the only family member who speaks a little German. I was there and I translated for six hours. As such I am an actual witness of the meeting. This was the reason why I read the book, especially the pages of our meetings. If you need anything further please come to us.

With kind regards

Mariangela Giolito Weiss

Minutes of a phone conversation with the mother of Udo Wiczorek, Isolde Wiczorek on the 03.12.2015

Did Udo speak in a South Tyrolean dialect? – *“Yes, she heard it.”*

Udo had never been to South Tyrol? – *“Never”*

Udo never practised the dialect? – *“Never”*

Udo drew pictures as a child? – *“Yes, but there are none left. He drew them in the caravan while on holidays: with a pencil, mountains, barbed wire, crosses.”*

Even double-decker aeroplanes? – *“It’s possible.”* Guns? *“Don’t know.”* *“As a grown up he also drew the pictures that are in the book.”*

Did Udo have nightmares as a child? – *“He was maybe four or five. They were not normal dreams. He would groan and was clearly in distress. When he woke up he would say ‘always faster’ and he meant the machine guns. It was very difficult to wake him. The doctor suggested holding his nose shut to wake him and tear him out of the dream. That worked.”*

Do you know anything about nightmares as an adult (have you heard about them)? – *“I only know what he told me. He moved out when he was 22 and has since been living with Daniela.”*

Did he tell you about travels to South Tyrol? – *“Yes”.*

He only met Bomm in 2010? *“Yes, although I can’t remember the exact year.”*

In an essay for school Udo described impressions from his dreams. The paper was torn up by the teacher because no one should write such gruesome things? – *“That’s correct. That’s why I had to meet with the teacher.”*

She then adds: *“Without Bomm nothing would have happened.”*

Minutes of a phone conversation with the hotel manager Rita Tschurtschenthaler, on 3.12.2015

Did Udo and Daniela Wieczorek stay with you in 1997? - *“Both visited a number of times.”*

Did you have any ideas of the first letter? - *“Only what I was told.”*

Did Udo and Daniela Wieczorek make frequent hikes? – *“Yes”*.

Is the char woman who first deciphered the letter still responsive? – *“I don’t know who that’s supposed to be.”*

Second cousin of Udo’s, Bianka Schneider describes in a face-to-face conversation on 30.11.2015 in Elchingen:

“As a child, Udo used to draw pictures in black and white of mountains and mountaineers, but there were also wounded soldiers, guns and only double-decker planes. There were many of these pictures, but they were all destroyed by his parents because they were so dreary. She will look for left overs.” Later I received the message that she had not been able to find anything.

The second cousin confirms that as a child Udo would speak in a different dialect for fun, even though he had never been to South Tyrol.

E-Mail from Prof (em) Dr.-Ing. Lothar Götttsching dated 11.12.2015 to me:

Hello Mr Hassler,

I really am not interested in these esotericism. This would, by the way, be far more suited to a different culture, most likely Hindu India.

The age of ink or wax cannot be dated to the required precision.

With kind regards

Lothar Götttsching

E-Mail from Prof (em) Dr.-Ing. Lothar Götttsching to Wieczorek detailing his results on the analysis of the paper used in Vinz’ letter:

----- Original-Nachricht -----

Datum: Thu, 7 Feb 2013 16:10:11 +0100

Von: Christel Goettsching

An: Udo und Daniela Wieczorek

Betreff: Re: Papieranalyse - Altersbestimmung

Liebe Kollegen,

mit schlechtem Gewissen kann ich Ihnen nunmehr reichlich verspätet meine Antwort zukommen lassen. Die einzige Laborantin an meinem ehemaligen Institut, die als nunmehrige Halbtagskraft derartige mikroskopische Faseranalysen durchführt, hatte

bis Ende Januar Urlaub.

Es ist eindeutig erkennbar, dass das mit einer hydrophoben Wachsschicht beidseitig versehene Schriftstück (als Feldpostbrief) nur aus Nadelholz-Zellstoff besteht, der seit 1875 anstelle von Lumpen (getragene Kleider aus Hanf und/oder Flachs mit oder ohne Baumwollanteile) zunehmend in der europäischen Papierindustrie eingesetzt wird.

Das Schriftstück enthält dagegen keine Anteile von Laubholz-Zellstoff (z.B. Birken-Zellstoff aus Nordeuropa oder Buchen-Zellstoff aus Mitteleuropa oder importierten Eukalyptus-Zellstoff aus Südeuropa oder Südamerika).

Aus Kostengründen und wegen der Verknappung an Nadelholz-Zellstoff hat man in den 1960er Jahren vor allem in Europa begonnen, den Nadelholz-Zellstoff anteilig durch Laubholz-Zellstoff zu ersetzen, so dass Schreib- und Druckpapiere aus einer Mischung dieser beiden Zellstofftypen hergestellt wurden und weiterhin werden. (An dieser Entwicklung war ich seit 1962 als junger Papieringenieur am Finnischen Zellstoff- und Papierindustrie maßgeblich im Rahmen von Labor-, halbtechnischen und industriellen Langzeitversuchen beteiligt.) Der Einsatz von Laubholz-Zellstoff in der europäischen Papierindustrie begann anfänglich in kleinen Mengen und setzte sich erst in den 1970er Jahren auf breiter Front durch, wobei Mitteleuropa einschließlich Deutschland (BRD) eine Vorreiterrolle einnahm.

Somit ist mit an Sicherheit grenzender Wahrscheinlichkeit festzustellen, dass das Papier des vorliegende Schriftstücks vor den 1970er produziert worden ist.

Leider enthält das Schriftstück bzw. dessen Papier keine weiteren Merkmale, die der genaueren Altersbestimmung dienen könnten. Die betrifft in erster Linie die für das Auge im Gegenlicht erkennbaren Wasserzeichen. Jede Papiermühle hatte in der Zeit der manuellen Büttenpapierherstellung sein eigenes Wasserzeichen als Marken- bzw. Herkunftszeichen (z.B. als stilisierten Ochsenkopf oder symbolhaften Bischofsstab), dessen Gestalt oder Motiv in engen Zeitabständen variiert wurde. Auf diese Weise lässt sich eine recht enge Zeiteinordnung anhand von Katalogen mit europäischen Wasserzeichen vornehmen.

Derartige Wasserzeichen wurden auch noch in der späteren Zeit bei der industriellen Papierherstellung bei höherwertigen Schreibpapieren verwendet. In wenigen Fällen verfügen Schreibpapiere aus heutiger Produktion auch noch über Wasserzeichen.

Ein weiterer Indikator für eine Altersbestimmung sind sogenannte optische Aufheller, die es erst seit den 1950er Jahren auf dem Markt gibt. In kleinsten Mengen dem Papier bei dessen Herstellung beigemischt, lassen sie das Papier unter ultraviolettem Licht einer UV-Lampe heller als unter Sonnen- oder künstlichem Licht erscheinen. Anfänglich erfolgte der Einsatz aus Kostengründen vornehmlich bei höherwertigen Schreibpapieren. Seit den 1960er Jahren entsprach der Einsatz optischer Aufheller dem Stand der Technik.

Vor diesem Hintergrund ist die Herstellung des Papiers des Schriftstücks für den

Zeitraum vor den 1960 Jahren zu datieren, da es keine optischen Aufheller enthält.

Eine genauere und eine frühere Altersbestimmung ist wegen fehlender Indikatoren anderer stofflicher oder visueller Art nicht möglich. Zu den weiteren Indikatoren würden beispielsweise Leimungsmittel gehören, die ein Papier überhaupt erst mit wässriger Tinte - ohne Auslaufen der Schrift - beschreibbar machen. Derartige Leimungsmittel haben sich seit den 1960er Jahren in ihrer chemischen Zusammensetzung im Übergang vom Baumharz zu verschiedenartigen synthetischen Leimungsmitteln geändert. Wegen des größeren Materialbedarfs konnte keine chemische Analyse von Leimungsmittel am Schriftstück durchgeführt werden.

Schließlich werden dem Papier zur Verbesserung seiner Opazität (Undurchsichtigkeit) neben den Fasern als Zellstoffe sogenannte Füllstoffe als weißes Pulver zugegeben, die einen Anteil um 10 Prozent ausmachen. Bis in die 1960er Jahre dominierte das Aluminiumsilikat Kaolin, das ebenfalls seit den 1960er langsam vom Calciumcarbonat (Kreide) oder auch vom Talkum oder Titandioxid teilweise verdrängt wurde.

Fazit:

Das Papier des mit einer Wachsschicht versehenen Schriftstücks ist vor den 1960er Jahren hergestellt wurde. Daraus kann aber nicht gefolgert werden, dass die Beschriftung ebenfalls auf das gleiche Alter zurückblicken kann.

Da in der globalen bzw. europäischen Papierindustrie in der Zeit vor dem Zweiten Weltkrieg im Gegensatz zur Zeit nach dem Zweiten Weltkrieg kaum Änderungen bei der stofflichen Zusammensetzung des erzeugten Papiers durchgeführt worden sind, kann - auch wegen fehlender Wasserzeichen - keine Datierung vor den 1960er Jahren vorgenommen werden. Die technische Entwicklung der Papierindustrie konzentrierte sich vor dem Zweiten Weltkrieg vornehmlich auf Innovationen beim Maschinenpark zugunsten signifikanter Erhöhungen der Produktivität (Breite und Geschwindigkeit der Papiermaschinen). Die zeitlichen Schwerpunkte der stofflichen Änderungen der Papierrezepturen lagen in der Mitte des 19. Jahrhunderts (von den Lumpen zu den Zellstoffen aus Nadelholz) und zu Beginn der zweiten Hälfte des 20. Jahrhunderts, wie oben ausgeführt.

Mit freundlichen Grüßen

Prof.(em.) Dr.-Ing. Lothar Götttsching
Institut für Papierfabrikation
Technische Universität Darmstadt

Darmstadt, den 7. Februar 2013

Additional information to the article

Concerning Fig. 1 (drawing as a child)

Unfortunately I was only able to recover one drawing from a diary of 1982. The bottom part of the image was drawn at the age of somewhere between five and seven, according to Wieczorek, which is in line with the dissonant perspective.

Little Udo even described impressions from his dreams in an essay for school. The paper was torn up by the teacher because no one should write such gruesome things and his mother was summoned by the teacher to discuss this. This episode is not revealed in the book, but told by Wieczorek and confirmed to me by his mother.

Concerning the emergency operation:

Wieczorek can describe this, as he made short notes after his operation.

Concerning hikes into the mountains without a map:

Surprising local knowledge: Sexten (79, 80, 82, 88, 89, 93, 96, 102, 104f, 116, 152, 159, 160, 178, 186, 240, 279); Centa (267, 310); confirmed local knowledge is underlined.

Concerning Wieczorek being suddenly filled with fear

Wieczorek is often on the look-out for mortal danger: 90, 92, 104, 106, 201.

Concerning flashbacks:

Flashbacks are frequent: (80, 97, 141, 153, 174, 177, 324, 342) most of the time about war occurrences (90, 93, 105, 117, 120, 122, 158, 166, 185, 216), showing images of the past.

Concerning spontaneous recognitions:

Recognising is described frequently: 52, 77, 81, 91, 97, 98, 100, 101, 102, 216, 218, 245, 283, 284, 292, 295, 304, 313, 319, 320, 321, 324, 328, 331; confirmed recognitions are underlined.

Personal message from Wieczorek to me: In Sexten he recognised and named a number of farmhouses. In one case he named the location of a goods pulley that no longer, but once existed. His wife confirms this as a witness.

Concerning local knowledge:

Ms Giolito told me during a walk through Centa that Wieczorek showed even more local knowledge but that after three years, she could not remember the details.

Concerning the location of death:

Vinz' relatives who are considered unsuspecting following the deception scenario, gave the location of death as Kreuzbergpass (301,323). This is very close to the Seikofel, the alleged location of Vinz' injury and also the location of finding the farewell letter. According to Holzer Seikofel and Kreuzbergpass were considered one and the same part of the front. The witnesses clearly assumed the location of the injury to be the location of death. The location of Vinz' injury is only confirmed after Wieczorek had already found the letter and stated that Vinz was injured on the Seikofel.

Concerning the discrepancy between the troop location and the spot where Wieczorek was injured:

In a one-on-one conversation with me Wieczorek explained: According to Fulvio Weiss, Vinz had been sick with tuberculosis following a previous deployment in Russia and had already

infected other members of his family on leave from the front. This was confirmed by Mrs Giolito. He could have been seen as unfit to serve and maybe this was the reason he went to Sexten. This is probably where, towards the end of July 1915 his lover Marie was killed through cannon-fire. In despair over her death and his incurable illness he could have volunteered to fight, as his statements after his operation suggests. It might also be the case that he was forced to fight given that the front was highly undermanned.

Concerning NDE in regression:

Both occurring: “NDE in addition to regression” and “NDE remembered in regression”.

Concerning flashbacks in CORT:

CORT may contain images of the past and things no longer in existence, but not in flashbacks.

Concerning premonitions in CORT:

Occurring in departing dreams but not decades ahead of time (e.g. Stevenson 1997, p. 703).

Concerning other traces of Josele

Mr Holzer told me that finding no traces would not be unusual for a defector who had been lowered by rope into no-mans-land. Recovering the body would have been life-threatening.

Concerning the discovery of the sundial:

Ms Gioloto confirmed in August 2016 that Wieczorek and her husband spoke at the same instant of time about the sundial, so Wieczorek didn't just copy him. Wieczorek says in the beginning he only saw the upper frame that surrounds the unfinished sundial. From my own inspection I conclude that this is believable if we accept that some items stood on top of the tall cupboard before the sundial as stated in the book (327, 328, 367).

Private reincarnation researcher
Uttenreuth, Germany
www.reinkarnation.de

DIPL.-ING. DIETER HASSLER
dieter.hassler@gmx.de

Questions and additional information after publication

Question: I wonder about the tin can and wooden box. The can must have been made of heavy metal, since I do not see how an ordinary can or ordinary wooden box could survive the weather for more than a few years.

Answer: good question, and one of the first, Udo Wieczorek asked himself. I forwarded the question to Udo and he replied (in German: my translation):

The can: It was three times enveloped in oilpaper, roofing felt and a mailbag as they could reconstruct from the remnants found. The stone material above is water-tight and reaches 1.5 m into the mountain. The place where the can was found was dry as a bone.

Even today, 100 years after WWI, you may still find intact cans in forgotten dugouts in the mountains. In this case the sheet metal was completely exposed to the weather without packaging and it is even thinner than the one of Vinz' rusty can. So, it is conceivable that “our” can can have lasted so long without being totally destroyed.

The wooden box (as told in the book): It crumbled between the fingers when pulled out from under the tree. It was totally grown into the root and thus well protected.

REFERENCES TO DREAM-BASED CASES

- Allgeier, K. (1984). *Du hast schon einmal gelebt / Wiedergeburt? Erinnerungen in der Hypnose*, München: Goldmann, ISBN: 3-442-11717-8, p. 141
- Allgeier, K. (1988). *Niemand stirbt für ewig / Vorstellungen und Wandlungen der Reinkarnation: Tod, Metamorphose und Wiedergeburt*, Zürich: Diana, ISBN: 3-905424-73-2, p. 301
- Banerjee, H.N. (1980). *Americans Who Have Been Reincarnated*, New York: Macmillan Publishing, ISBN: 0-02-506740-0, p. 169, 171, 172
- Berger, A. & Berger, J. (1991). *Reincarnation / Fact or Fable*, London: Aquarian Press, ISBN: 1-85538-111-7, pp. 16-19
- Bowman, C. (2003). *Return from Heaven / Beloved Relatives Reincarnated within your Family*, New York: Harper Torch, ISBN: 0-06-103044-9, p. 13
- Bowman, C. (2016). *Vendorswagens, A Dream Case*, <http://www.carolbowman.com/library/vendorswagens/>
- Carpenter, S. (1995). *Past Lives / True Stories of Reincarnation*, London: Virgin Books, ISBN: 0-86369-906-5, p. 88
- Cranston, S., & Williams, C. (1984). *Reincarnation / A New Horizon in Science, Religion, and Society*, New York: Julian Press, ISBN: 0-517-55496-8, p. 82
- Fenwick, P., & Fenwick, E. (1999). *Past Lives / An Investigation into Reincarnation Memories*, London: Headline Book Publ., ISBN: 0-7472-5548-2, p. 94
- Gershom, Y. (1997). *Kehren die Opfer des Holocaust wieder?*, Rudolf Geering, ISBN: 3-7235-1002-7 ((1992) *Beyond the Ashes*; (1996) *From Ashes to Healing*)
- Grubbs, A. (2006). *Chosen to Believe / Present Dreams Past Lives*, Jonesboro, Georgia: Pink Elephant Press, ISBN: 0-9772975-0-0
- Hardo, T. (2012). *Wiedergeburt / Die Beweise ...und die Bedeutung für neues Bewusstsein / erweiterte Neuauflage*, Göllesheim: Silberschnur, ISBN: 978-3-89845-352-3, p. 75, 80, 86
- Hassler, D. (2011). *...früher, da war ich mal groß. Und.../ Indizienbeweise für ein Leben nach dem Tod und die Wiedergeburt / Band 1: Spontanerinnerungen kleiner Kinder an ihr „früheres Leben“*, Aachen: Shaker Media, ISBN: 978-3-86858-646-6
- Hassler, D. (2015). *Geh' zurück in eine Zeit... / Indizienbeweise für ein Leben nach dem Tod und die Wiedergeburt / Band 2a: Rückführungen in „frühere Leben“ und deren Nachprüfung*, Aachen: Shaker Media, ISBN: 978-3-95631-359-2
- Hassler, D. (2015a). *Geh' zurück in eine Zeit... / Indizienbeweise für ein Leben nach dem Tod und die Wiedergeburt / Band 2b: Rückführungen in „frühere Leben“ und deren Nachprüfung*, Aachen: Shaker Media, ISBN: 978-3-95631-360-8
- Holzer, H. (1970). *Born Again / The Truth about Reincarnation*, New York: Doubleday, ISBN: none, p. 247, 250
- Holzer, H. (1994). *Life Beyond / Compelling Evidence for Past Lives and Existence After Death*, Lincolnwood (Chicago): Contemporary, ISBN: 0-8092-3577-3, p. 185, 336
- Holzer, H. (1994a). *The Psychic Side of Dreams*, St. Paul, Minnesota: Llewellyn Publ., ISBN: 0-87542-369-8, p. 179

Jacobson, N. O. (1973). *Leben nach dem Tod / Über Parapsychologie und Mystik*, Düsseldorf: Econ, ISBN: 3-430-15004-3, p. 75

Karlen, B. (1997). *Und die Wölfe heulten / Eine Autobiographie*, Basel: Perseus, ISBN: 3-907564-25-1

Kent, J. H. (2003). *Past Life Memories as a Confederate Soldier*, Huntsville, Arizona: ZARK Mountain, ISBN: 1-886940-84-3

Krippner, Stanley; Bogzaran, Fariba; Carvalho, André Percia (2002) *Extraordinary Dreams and how to Work with Them*, New York: SUNY-Press, ISBN: 0-7914-5258-1, p. 128f

Lasch, E. E. (2004). *Sie sind wieder da / Eine andere Sicht unserer Geschichte*, Singen: Buchagentur Günter Heiß, ISBN: 3-9808795-7-7, p. 61

Lenz, F. (1979). *Lifetimes / True Accounts of Reincarnation*, New York: Bobbs-Merrill, ISBN: 0-672-52490-2, p. 34

Lucas, W. B. (1993). *Regression Therapy / A Handbook for Professionals/ Vol. 1: Past Life Therapy*, Crest Park, California: Deep Forest Press, ISBN: 1-882530-01-2, p. 251

Lucas, W. B. (1993a). *Regression Therapy / A Handbook for Professionals/ Vol. 2: Past Life Therapy*, Crest Park, California: Deep Forest Press, ISBN: 1-882530-02-0, p. 211, 250

McDonald, P. (1985). *Dreams / Night Language of the Soul*, Baton Rouge, Louisiana, Laguna Beach, California: Topaz Press, ISBN: 0-914255-01-0, p. 219

Mills, A. (1994). *Nightmares in Western Children: An Alternative Interpretation suggested by Data in Three Cases*, The Journal of the American Society for Psychical Research, Vol. 88, 309 - 325

Muller, K. E. (1970). *Reincarnation - based on facts*, London: Psychic Press Ltd., ISBN: 853840105

Rivas, T. (2016). *Dreams about previous lives*, <http://txtxs.nl/artikel.asp?artid=784>

Rogo, D. S. (1985). *The Search for Yesterday / A critical Examination of the Evidence for Reincarnation*, New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc., ISBN: 0-13-797028-5, pp. 28-32

Schlotterbeck, K. (1987). *Living Your Past Lives: The Psychology of Past Life Regression*, New York: Ballantine, ISBN: 0-345-34028-0, p. 24

Schmidt, K. O. (1962). *Wir leben nicht nur einmal / 111 Rückerinnerungen an frühere Leben, Berichte und Tatsachen*, Argenbühl-Eglofstal: Heinrich Schwab, ISBN: 3-7964-0062-0, p. 124, 157, 161, 256

Stearn, J. (1994). *The Search for a Soul / Taylor Caldwell's Past Lives*, New York: Berkley Books, ISBN: 0-425-14366-X, p. 136

Steiger, B. (1973). *The Enigma of Reincarnation / the Incredible, but Factual, Case Histories of those who have Lived Before*, New York: ace books, ISBN: none, p. 28, 34

Steiger, B. (1996). *You have Lived Before and You will Live Again / Dramatic Case Histories of Reincarnation*, Nevada City: Blue Dolphin, ISBN: 0-931892-29-5

Steiger, B. (1996a). *Returning from the Light / Using Past Lives to Understand the Present and Share the Future*, London, New York: Signet, ISBN: 0-451-18623-0, p. 1

Stemman, R. (1995). *The man in her dreams was her past life husband*, Reincarnation International, No. 5, 16

Stevenson, I. (1997). *Reincarnation and Biology Vol. 2*, London: Praeger, ISBN: 0-275-95284-3, p. 737, 888, 1386

Stevenson, I. (2003). *European Cases of the Reincarnation Type*, Jefferson, North Carolina: McFarland, ISBN: 0-7864-1458-8

Ward, P. v. (2008). *The Soul Genome / Science and Reincarnation*, Tucson, Arizona: Fenestra Books, ISBN: 978-1-58736-995-7, p. 26

Wieczorek, U., & Bomm, M. (2015). *Seelenvermächtnis / Udo W.: Mein zweites Leben*, Meßkirch: Verlag Gmeiner, ISBN: 978-3-8392-1782-5

Private reincarnation researcher
Uttenreuth, Germany
www.reinkarnation.de

DIPL.-ING. DIETER HASSLER
dieter.hassler@gmx.de